

GENDER DIVERSITY: A CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF ITS ANTECEDENTS AND CONSEQUENCES

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Abstract

Purpose – The aim of this paper is to understand the growing concept of gender diversity. It focuses on the idea of gender diversity and develops a conceptual framework including various propositions related to the antecedents and consequences of gender diversity. **Design/methodology/approach** – This is a review paper based on the act of combining ideas of gender diversity from existing research journals and articles on gender diversity. Authors analysed selected papers on gender diversity to propose a conceptual framework that shows the antecedents and consequences of gender diversity. **Findings** –The study reveals empowering environment and organisational culture as the antecedents of Gender diversity. Further, the study indicates that gender diversity plays a vital role in developing positive outcomes such as High productivity, employee engagement and Improvement in innovation. **Practical Implications** – This paper offers opportunities for researchers to explore discoveries in gender diversity and also helps to understand the ways the organizations can develop gender diversity practices at workplace.

Keywords: Gender Diversity, Diversity, Empowering Environment, Organization Culture, High Productivity, Employee Engagement, Innovation

INTRODUCTION

Companies now days focus on hiring a gender diverse workforce to promote equality at all levels in the highly competitive environment of today. Women in the corporate sector have made amazing contributions to success. But not everyone recognises the importance that women add to businesses; instead, they are thought of as playing a supporting role. The dedication of women in the corporate sector is essential to the success and growth of company globally. The term 'gender' refers to the socially created identities, roles, and expectations associated with males and females (Patt et al., 2009). Different assessments of men and women have emerged over time as a result of gender beliefs.

While there have been some hopeful advancements in gender equality at work, efforts to close the gender gap have halted. There are still significant differences between men and women in a number of areas, including the labour market, remuneration for work of similar value, the proportion of women in managerial and high-paying occupations, and the allocation of unpaid care tasks. It will take proactive and innovative policies from a number of global stakeholders, including governments, businesses, employers' and workers' groups, and civil society, to achieve economic empowerment and gender equality for women. The private sector's

performance on gender equality, however, varies greatly depending on the nation, industry, and size of the company, as well as corporate leadership and culture, with small and medium-sized businesses facing the most difficulties.

Bem (1993) affirms that from the pre-Revolutionary War era and the crafting of laws and the Constitution, which excluded the rights of women, these fundamental ideas on defining gender roles persisted into American society. Many of these restrictions persisted until the Supreme Court ruled in the 1970s that equal rights applied to sex as well (Bem 1993).

Despite the Equal Employment Opportunity Act of 1972's (EEOA) historic passage nearly 50 years ago, there is still a gender gap in the engineering and construction industries (Hatch 2008; Harrison 2010). The study begins by reviewing the literature on gender and diversity to show its breadth, depth, and intellectual heritage. Additionally, it creates a conceptual framework with a number of hypotheses on the causes and effects of gender diversity.

Understanding the evolving concept of gender diversity and its connected ideas is the main goal of this article. It creates a conceptual framework that includes numerous assertions linked to the causes and effects of gender diversity with a focus on the concept of gender diversity.

GENDER DIVERSITY: AN OVERVIEW

According to Thomas (1990), managing diversity in an organisation entails managing individual differences so that all employee groups may successfully carry out their tasks. As a result, the objective is to establish a contemporary work environment where everyone feels valued in their roles.

One of the core tenets of the European Social Charter, which the European Commission established in 1961, is gender equality and women's rights (European Social Charter). It contains numerous proposals for treating men and women equally in society, politics, and the workplace. The phrase "gender role" was first used in a study by John Money (1995), who also served as its first coiner. The basic assumption in the concept of DM is that work-teams consist of a diverse population. There are different aspects of the diversity, like age, sex, ethnicity, race and disability, but also the personality or the style of work (Lawthom 2003). Some factors can be shaped by individuals, while some others are beyond individual's control. Some of them affect how a person is perceived by a social environment, while some others can be a source of discrimination in the workplace. "Fair representation of an individual from diverse sexes, which centres to fair ratio of women, men, and other is gender diversity" is the definition of gender diversity (Systma, 2006). Shore et al. (2009) Affirmative action and equal employment opportunity strategies are the foundations of the diversity management concept. In turn, the Civil Rights Movement that took place in the USA during the 20th century gave rise to these ideas.

"The degree to which a person's gender identity, role, or expression differs from the cultural standards set for people of a given sex," is the definition of gender diversity. This term is gaining popularity as a more affirming and possibly less stigmatising way to describe persons who do not fit into any given cultural standard than gender nonconformity (Gender Spectrum,

2013). Recent gender diversity studies confirmed less than 10% representation by women in all billets, including senior executives, middle management, and line workers. This persists even though more than 21% of engineering graduates are female (Allison et al., 2017).

Devnew et al. (2018) indicates that better communications, improved stakeholder relations, and increased innovation are examples of non-financial improvements. Due to this talent drain, the industry misses out on the advantages of gender diversity Sunindijo and Kamardeen (2017). Women's participation on audit and compliance committees lowers an organization's risk position and increases the likelihood of greater returns because they have a lower risk tolerance (Pritchard et al., 2018). Gender diversity may encourage improved communication, stakeholder participation, and financial outcomes, according to prior study according to Pritchard and Miles (2018).

Gender diversity refers to the extent to which an individual deviates from the norms and standards accepted for people of a particular sex in terms of gender personality, occupation, or articulation.

DEVELOPMENT OF THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

In this section, authors have identified few essential antecedents and consequences to establish relationship with gender diversity. These antecedents and consequences offer insight into and a chance to learn about "antecedents of gender diversity and how it contributes to achieving desirable organisational goals".

Figure: 1: Conceptual Framework

The objective of this study is to present formal propositions that will help future researchers better comprehend the concept of gender diversity. These claims are based on individual traits, how they affect gender diversity, and how gender diversity has an impact. These propositions are based on the gender diversity literature that is currently available. Therefore, this work can stimulate the attention of diversity academics to further investigate the gender diversity construct. The important propositions are discussed next.

EMPOWERING ENVIRONMENT AND GENDER DIVERSITY

According to one definition, empowerment is a "multi-dimensional social process that aids individuals in taking charge of their own life. It is a process that helps people develop their power so they can use it in their own lives, communities, and societies by taking action on topics they see as essential, according to Page and Czuba, (1999). In a similar vein, "women's ability to make strategic life choices where that ability had previously been denied them" is referred to as "women's empowerment" (Malhotra et al., 2009). Therefore, retaining the advantages of women at the individual, household, community, and wider levels depends on empowerment (Malhotra et al., 2009). It entails improving the position of women through literacy, education, training, and awareness-building as per Alvarez and Lopez, (2013). Women's empowerment, then, is all about empowering women to make decisions that will have a significant impact on their lives across a range of national issues. Due to the pervasiveness of gender inequity across all cultures, the topic of women's empowerment and gender equality is at the top of political agendas everywhere. Comparatively to affluent countries, gender inequality is quite prevalent in developing nations (Ahmed et al., 2001). Most notably, despite the government's vigorous efforts to address such issues, gender-based discrimination and disparities are quite noticeable in Ethiopia. As a result, the country's progress is still hampered by low levels of women's empowerment and a wide gender gap (Environmental Protection Authority, 2012). Even though the nation is developing in many ways, the prospect of its sustainability is in doubt given the significant gender gap.

Gender equality is a second almost-related but equally significant idea in this essay. Warth and Koparanova (2012) defines gender equality as an individual's "rights, duties, and opportunities will not rely on whether they are born male or female". A scenario where "all human beings are free to develop their personal capacities and make choices without the constraints created by strict gender norms; that the diverse aspirations and needs of women and men are acknowledged, respected, and favoured equally" is another definition of gender equality (Holzner et al., 2010). The absence of gender-based discrimination is the ultimate objective of gender equality as per Alvarez and Lopez, (2013).

Studies have proven that gender equality and the empowerment of women are essential for sustainable development. Therefore, it is claimed that gender equality is a concern for human rights, a requirement for sustainable development, and an indicator of it (Alvarez and Lopez, 2013). Additionally, it is stated that gender inequality is pervasive throughout all cultures and that sustainable development 92 is impossible to attain without making major efforts to address it (Stevens, 2010). Furthermore, UN Women 93 (2014) correctly said that achieving gender equality is crucial for building a just and sustainable world 94 as well as for enhancing women's roles in supporting their families and 95 communities. However, if gender equality is not upheld, the development of the country will be slowed. According to Stevens (2010), "a growing number of studies indicate that 99 gender inequalities are extracting large economic costs and leading 100 to social injustices and environmental degradation around the 101 world," which is in keeping with this viewpoint.

P1: Empowering environment is positively related to gender diversity.

ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND GENDER DIVERSITY

An organization's culture can be thought of as a set of common values and ideas that provide its members a better understanding of how the organisation works and set expectations for how they should behave. By giving employees a framework to internalise expectations regarding corporate responsibilities and behaviours, organisational culture largely functions as a control mechanism for the organisation (Deshpande and Webster, 1989).

This is how organisational culture may affect how diversity affects company performance. For instance, Williams and O'Reilly (1998) indicate that organisational culture may be a useful strategy for managers to promote unity in their thorough literature analysis on the consequences of diversity.

As more women enter the managerial ranks, there has been significant progress in the area of gender diversity (Elsass and Graves, 1997).

Researchers recently discovered that various forms of diversity inside businesses have various results (Pelled et al., 1999). Pelled (1996), in particular, makes the case that nonvisible qualities affect performance in quite different ways from visible ones. Therefore, understanding how one type of diversity affects the firm may offer little to no insight into how another type may have an impact. We aim to broaden this research and more deeply investigate the causes and effects of gender diversity.

Performance improvements may be facilitated by gender diversity in management positions (Williams and O'Reilly, 1998). Businesses that want to expand try to reduce costs by distributing risks among a larger group of people and benefiting from the transfer of managerial or technical skills (Pearce, 1982). Therefore, a company can pursue growth at its finest when it has the right and necessary human capital to oversee a rising business. Cultural variety can offer the depth of expertise and experience which results in the growth of the company. (McLeod et al., 1996).

In addition, if an organisation succeeds in overcoming resistance to change in order to welcome diversity, it should be well-equipped to deal with other kinds of change as well, such as expansion (Iles and Hayers, 1997).

Gender diversity may have benefits for the market. Women, especially those in managerial positions, may contribute additional expertise, experience, and flexibility as well as cultural awareness, understanding, and sensitivity necessary to meet the needs of new market segments as corporations enter or acquire organisations in new markets (Cox, 1994).

Businesses that want to expand must use more resources to make up for early operational inefficiencies. Growth-oriented companies may be able to take advantage of their human capital, which includes the variety of skills, knowledge, and abilities of its personnel. Diverse workforces can foster creativity and flexibility, which could be advantageous for businesses looking to expand (Richard, 2000).

A company implementing a downsizing strategy, on the other hand, looks for operational efficiencies. Although having a diverse pool of human resources might improve the quality of

ideas, among other things, it can also increase costs because a more diverse group requires more coordination and control (Jehn, 1995). For businesses that are downsizing, the increased expenditures related to diversity could be a significant disadvantage. For instance, Richard (2000) discovered that a growth strategy could mitigate the association between firm-level ethnic diversity and business success. Racially diverse businesses that prioritised growth outperformed those following a shrinking strategy in terms of performance.

Gender diversity is thought to have effects that are comparable to those of other observable diversity qualities like race (Pelled, 1996), therefore growth should also have an impact on how gender diversity affects firm performance. Furthermore, it is conceivable that this interaction may become more intense at the management level, where crucial choices that affect the entire company are developed and put into action.

Based on the work of Quinn and his colleagues, the Competing Values Framework is a generally accepted view of organisational culture (see Cameron and Quinn, 1999, for references). According to the concept (Cameron and Freeman, 1991; Cameron and Quinn, 1999; Deshpande et al., 1993), organisational cultures can be distinguished based on their dominant organisational characteristics, bonding mechanisms, leadership styles, and overall strategic emphases.

P2: Organization culture is positively related to gender diversity

GENDER DIVERSITY AND HIGHER PRODUCTIVITY

The impacts of gender diversity among managers who are positioned in hierarchical positions under the top management are currently the subject of very little research. Women who are overall managers have a favourable correlation with ROS, ROA, ROI and ROE, according to Shrader et al. (1997). When looking at midlevel managers as a whole, Dwyer et al. (2003) investigated whether the impact of diversity on company performance is more completely recognised. They pointed out that having a gender-diverse management team promotes growth-oriented businesses that emphasise flexibility and creativity. A U-shaped association between gender diversity in middle and lower management and organisational success, as assessed by ROE and worker productivity, was hypothesised by McMillan-Capehart and Simerly (2008). Curvilinear correlations were also hypothesised by Richard et al. (2013), but no notable outcomes were seen.

Since studies (Heilman and Haynes, 2005; Heilman and Okimoto, 2007) have shown that women frequently experience the negative effects of gender stereotyping when they work in teams with males, impeding team performance and functioning, a focus on gender diversity is essential.

According to Schwab et al., (2015), social engagement, gender diversity, and employee performance are all correlated with one another. When men and women demonstrate different knowledge, thinking, informational, and problem-solving capacities, gender diversity may have an impact on performance.

Women in the savings and loan sector are more likely to be employed and promoted into a specific employment level when there are a lot of women working at that level, according to Cohen et al. (1998). Women in low-ranking positions are more likely to quit when there are more women in senior positions, according to Elvira and Cohen (2001). According to Bilimoria (2006), there is a direct correlation between the number of female executives working for a Fortune 500 business and the number of female directors on the board.

According to Cohen and Broschak (2013), the correlation between the number of new management positions filled by men and the proportion of female managers is initially positive but thereafter plateaus and turns negative.

The majority of research on demographic diversity in management has focused on how gender diversity on boards affects organisational performance. Studies on "diversity in the boardroom" have sought to identify the "magic number" of female executives. Some people have discovered that performance is maximised at a critical mass of 30%.

According to several studies, gender diversity on boards has a good effect on financial metrics. As an illustration, Mnguez-Vera and López-Martnez (2010) demonstrate that having women on the board has a favourable impact on the return on assets (ROA)

In a global perspective, the meta-analysis of Post and Byron (2015) identifies a marginally positive relationship between board gender diversity and firm financial performance. Reguera-Alvarado et al. (2017) found a positive relation between gender diversity at the board and financial performance, measured with the Tobin's Q.

There is a dearth of diversity-related research at the organisational level of analysis. The few studies that have looked at the relationship between the gender makeup of the workforce and various organisational performance metrics have produced conflicting findings. For instance, several scholars proposed that worker diversity has advantages for business performance. According to Ali et al. (2014), there is a positive linear link between employee productivity and the gender diversity of the entire workforce. According to Ali et al. (2011), there is a direct correlation between workplace gender diversity and worker productivity.

According to Polzer et al., (2002), interpersonal congruence (the degree to which a group confirms each member's self-view) is the sole factor that positively affects group creativity.

P3: Gender diversity is positively related to higher productivity

GENDER DIVERSITY AND INNOVATION

A difficult and unresolved question in the literature on innovation is how gender diversity affects innovation performance in various innovative situations.

According to (Davis et al.,1993); Ramanujan and Cooper,1994), a firm's innovation activity can be thought of as a human information-processing task in which input informational cues are interpreted and manipulated to produce task outcomes. In contrast, the degree to which firms can benefit from gender diversity depends on task characteristics.

According to several empirical research (Jackson et al., 1995; O'Reilly et al., 1997), workgroup gender diversity fosters innovation and creativity within the group by producing informational advantages. Additionally, gender diversity provides organisations with social benefits by bringing a range of value systems and behavioural patterns. Women tend to be amiable, pleasant with others, and process-oriented, whereas men are more forceful, opinionated, and task-oriented (Karakowsky and Siegel, 1999; Myaskovsky et al., 2005; Wood, 1987). Therefore, the presence of women should aid in facilitating team members' communication, increasing their mutual understanding and information sharing. Women enhance a team's interactions with partners and external relationships Joshi and Jackson (2003).

The benefits of more knowledge and social interaction from gender diversity may ensure team performance. A propensity for gender-mixed groups to outperform homogenous groups has also been confirmed by meta-analytic research (Bowers et al., 2000; Williams and O'Reilly, 1998; Wood, 1987).

Since non-repetitive jobs in innovation are typically ambiguous and complex by nature, knowledge workers must collaborate with a diverse range of people and draw on a broad body of information in order to be successful (Janz et al., 1997).

According to the "value-in-diversity" perspective (Cox et al., 1991), gender diversity can improve information accessibility and bring about a variety of viewpoints and knowledge. These two premises make sure that one viewpoint or body of knowledge does not predominate over all other considerations in a decision (Ely and Thomas, 2001; Jehn et al., 1999).

Generally speaking, women are more risk-averse and risk-aware than men Adams and Funk (2012). As a result, they are able to recognise project hazards that go beyond men's views and offer a perspective that complements men's ideas. This presumption lessens a male-dominated R&D team's propensity for taking excessive risks and empowers such a team to choose thoroughly scrutinised initiatives (Jehn et al., 1999; Van Knippenberg et al., 2004). Additionally, as women tend to hold some sorts of knowledge that men do not, they can increase the integration of varied ideas to create innovative solutions or directly propose fresh ideas for problems that already exist (Schiebinger, 2008). In conclusion, an increase in the proportion of women in R&D teams can expand the diversity of knowledge, provide new kinds of integrated knowledge, and result in more innovation outputs for the company given the same amount of innovation input (stergaard et al., 2011; Woodman et al., 1993). We gather data from the R&D team members we spoke with to support the informational advantages of gender diversity in R&D teams. Joshi and Jackson (2003) demonstrated how gender diversity could increase team relationships with external groups, facilitating the acquisition of knowledge and ideas.

Because female members may reassure their team and help the R&D professionals cope with uncertainty, the social benefits of having female R&D members are critical for innovation efficiency in this situation. Additionally, when the market is unclear, teamwork and communication among R&D staff members become crucial Bechky and Okhuysen (2011).

"Team traits should not be interpreted as the sum of what distinguishes the team members," write Blomqvist and Frennberg (2010) Groups have a unique dynamic that influences both the thinking and behaviour of the individuals inside them as well as the group as a whole. In light of this claim, we suggest that gender diversity the proportion of men and women in a team and the dynamics that result from their collaboration favours innovation and motivates R&D teams to create initiatives that call for significant changes.

The literature notes that including women in teams increases decision-making and soft management abilities as well as creativity and innovation (Bagshaw, 2004; Dessler, 2001). Generally speaking, women have less experience and a different professional trajectory than males, but this doesn't necessarily mean that they have less knowledge; rather, it shows that their human and social capital backgrounds are extremely diverse, which could improve performance (Singhet al., 2008). Additionally, women's interest in technology has increased as a result of their increased educational attainment and higher expectations for their job and careers, which may allow them to reinterpret the gender preconceptions that have historically prevented them from working in this field (Eriksson 2007).

Furthermore, a recent study by Ostergaard et al. (2011) discovered that companies with a gender composition that is more evenly distributed are more likely to innovate than companies with a high concentration of one gender. Since diversity affects how knowledge is generated and utilised during the invention process, it is said that innovation is an interactive process that is facilitated by diversity among individuals who interact (Ostergaard et al., 2011, p. 502). Apestegua, Azmat, and Iriberry (2011) also assert that mixed teams performed best, suggesting a possible link between gender diversity and effective teamwork. In addition, gender diversity may strengthen the organization's contacts with outside parties, enabling group members to collaborate with individuals from different groups and gain expertise and ideas (Joshi & Jackson, 2008) therefore, fostering radical innovations.

The nature of the tasks completed, which affects how people relate to one another and combine their perspectives, is a key moderator between team composition and effectiveness (Gist et al., 1987; Gladstein, 1984; Haas, 2010; Yu, 2002), and the behaviour of women in social contexts is highly sensitive to the specifics of the context (Ben-Ner, Kong, and Putterman, 2004; Houser & Schunk, 2009).

P4: Gender diversity is positively related to Innovation.

GENDER DIVERSITY AND EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT

The proportion of women working in the U.S. has gradually climbed over the past 25 years. 53.4% of males and 46.6% of women are currently employed in the United States. Due to this demographic transformation, which was sparked by the civil rights movement and supported by government law, businesses are now more interested in effectively handling diversity-related challenges (Kochan et al., 2003; Mannix and Neale, 2005).

Some experts contend that no single perspective adequately captures the complex relationship between diversity and performance, both theoretically and empirically, and that it is crucial to

take context into account when analysing the diversity-performance relationship. Examples of context include employee engagement levels, interpersonal congruence, and human resource practises (Carter et al., 2007; Horwitz, 2005; Kochan et al., 2003; Pelled, 1996; Pelled, et al., 1999).

Using Kahn's (1990, 1992) research as a foundation, we propose that high levels of engagement at the business-unit level (a sign of good intergroup relations) sustain a safe psychological environment where gender-diverse groups may be able to achieve high levels of interpersonal congruence, reducing dysfunctional conflict and improving business outcomes. Conversely, low engagement levels (a sign of bad intergroup interactions) may trigger dysfunctional conflict between men and women, which would have a detrimental impact on economic success. We postulate that the relationship between gender diversity and performance is tempered by business-unit level participation based on psychological presence theory and research.

Employee engagement may be improved by changing employee engagement procedures. Employee engagement has been identified as a critical element in improving employee performance in firms by researchers including Garg et al., (2018). Social engagement is one of these aspects, and it is seen to be essential for raising employee performance. For instance, Muhammad and Hamdy (2005) discovered that when workers have satisfying collegial relationships, they tend to work harder. Yousef (2017) additionally made the case that teamwork, social contacts, and having supportive coworkers are all crucial for improving employee performance. In a similar vein, Kwon et al., (2016) found that employee performance is influenced by the social interactions within an organisation.

Diversity-oriented HR practises may reduce prejudice during critical personnel decision-making times, but without fostering a diverse workplace culture, they are less likely to eradicate the relational sources of prejudice that arise on a daily basis and affect employees' perceptions and experiences of diversity orientation (Green and Kalev, 2008; Nishii, 2013).

Even though work engagement reflects employees' active harnessing of their personal resources toward work roles and engaged employees are more motivated and committed to perform behaviours within and beyond their roles (Rich et al., 2010), less empirical work has been devoted to exploring diversity practises and climate as organisational precursors of work engagement among employees (Downey et al., 2015; Kumar et al., 2018).

The term "diversity atmosphere" refers to the notion that all members of a work group, regardless of their backgrounds, are treated equitably and incorporated into the workplace (Chung et al., 2015). Diversity policies would help all employees and encourage their positive attitudes and conduct by creating a diverse work environment (Ashikali and Groeneveld, 2015). We therefore anticipate that an environment of diversity can relate practises in HR that are diversity-focused with employee work engagement.

Employees would view such policies as advantageous to them and so create social exchange relationships with the organisation since diversity-oriented HR practises signal fair and supportive treatment to all social groups in the workplace (Jehn and Bezrukova, 2004). To

preserve this social exchange relationship, employees are prone to respond with positive attitudes and behaviours such developing and sharing favourable impressions of diversity practises as well as participating passionately in their work responsibilities (Li and Frenkel, 2017). Mousa and Chaouli (2021) revealed that Gender diversity has a positive impact on organisational commitment, job satisfaction, and engagement.

P5: Gender diversity is positively related to employee engagement.

A conceptual model on the antecedents and consequences of gender diversity has been developed based on the propositions and discussion presented above.

CONCLUDING REMARKS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Implementing gender diversity strategies is now very important for an organisation to continue and survive continuously in the current competitive business environment.

The focal point of gender diversity in the workplace should be to increase engagement, productivity, and innovation. The pertinent gender diversity literature is discussed in this paper. It also looks into the antecedents and consequences of gender diversity and develops a set of propositions to evaluate different relationships.

It has been observed that empowering environment, organization culture, high productivity, improved innovation and employee engagement are positively related to gender diversity.

An organization cannot think of big success without developing gender diversity practices in the workplace. Hence as consequence or outcome, it is proposed that gender diversity is positively related to employee engagement and higher productivity.

Though it can be challenging to develop a study on gender diversity due to the complexity and practical challenges of looking at the phenomena from many angles but still this field has a tonne of untapped potential for young academics and researchers.

Everyone, both personally and institutionally, has been concerned about gender diversity, especially women. Indeed, this conceptual framework and the models that have been suggested are sparse, focusing mostly on the antecedents and consequences of gender diversity.

Every organisation is currently struggling with how to implement gender diversity initiatives. It takes time, money, and resources to put up systems for developing diversity practises in a business. Educational institutions are likewise looking for strategies to promote the same. This notion and its conceptual underpinnings can be adopted by diversity academics as their future research plan in order to put it to an empirical test. The top firms in the world can take the initiative and commit time and other resources to training their employees on gender diversity and the adoption of diversity policies. As a result, this study aids diversity experts in their understanding of how gender diversity has evolved in the workplace. Researchers with a variety of goals and interests can use this topic of gender diversity to their advantage in their upcoming work.

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